

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

IMPETUS: The role of citizen science in European water management and policy

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable water management is a global challenge. While the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6 specifically addresses clean water and sanitation, water pollution is intertwined across many goals and has implications for food security, health, wellbeing, biodiversity, and ecosystems.¹ In Europe, despite increased awareness about the importance of sustainable water management, and legislation such as the European Water Directive Framework, a complete regional picture of water quality does not exist.² This is echoed at the global level. To address this challenge, the UN recognises the significance of incorporating non-traditional data sources, such as citizen science, into water monitoring practices.

This policy brief describes the challenges of sustainable water management and how citizen science and public participation can help. This is just one example of an issue within the environmental regulation and climate resilience agenda that could benefit from citizen science. The brief provides a set of very practical recommendations for national water regulators, for national level environment agencies and for the Directorate General for the Environment of the European Commission about how to support citizen science initiatives to address some of these issues in water management.

WHAT DO WE MEAN BY WATER MANAGEMENT POLICY AND HOW DOES IT WORK IN THE EU CONTEXT?

EU water policy takes place through the consistent implementation of the European Water Framework Directive (WFD),³ which aligns with the UN SDG 6 on access to clean water and sanitation. The WFD requires Member States to identify river basins within their territory and assign them to River Basin Districts (RBD), the spatial unit for all planning and monitoring tools and activities under the WFD.

The WFD also recognises a key role for public participation in water management. Despite this emphasis, there is no practical guidance on the opportunities for effectively leveraging citizen participation.

¹ UN Environment Programme (2016). Snapshot of the world's water quality: towards a global assessment. Available at: <https://www.unep.org/resources/publication/snapshot-report-worlds-water-quality>

² <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/environmental-science/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2024.1371048/full>

³ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en

The WFD helps to raise awareness and supports Member States to develop aligned policies. However, the institutions tasked with operationalising these policies often face several challenges for successful water management, such as:

a. *Insufficient data for monitoring*

Water quality is difficult to observe at high spatial and temporal resolutions; it is expensive and typically requires trained specialists in the field and in laboratories. Water quality monitoring by statutory bodies has declined to a point where the spatial and temporal frequency of the monitoring is insufficient to fully understand the complex range of pollution sources and their impacts.⁴ Also, most small water bodies are not covered by the WFD monitoring,⁵ meaning that small water bodies are the least monitored freshwater resources, with significant gaps in terms of spatial and temporal coverage. For example, in Ireland less than 10% of the river sites in the national water quality monitoring programme are on small streams.⁶ The issue of severe data gaps for monitoring small water bodies in national water quality monitoring programmes is worryingly similar across other European countries.

b. *Poor coordination and ineffective targeting of resources for water management*

Ideas and practical knowledge about water management are often distributed between stakeholders and potentially difficult to access, or dispersed across geographic regions. This means localised actions are finding scaling challenging, and the longer term sustainability of actions and initiatives is called into question. Successful water management requires the active participation and commitment of *all* involved stakeholders: citizen, decision and policy makers, and (private) data aggregators and scientists. This requires in-depth understanding of their motivations, incentives and barriers for participating.⁷

c. *Lack of public trust in stakeholders responsible for water management*

The lack of information and awareness surrounding mass pollution has caused a steep decline in public trust in water sector management, heavily damaging the relationship between consumers and suppliers.⁸ Recent WFD assessments suggest that just 38% of European waters (rivers, lakes and transitional coastal waters) meet the required standard.⁹ In the UK in particular, there is widespread dissatisfaction around waterbody pollution, with frequent media coverage highlighting this. In 2023, Ofwat, the UK's water sector regulator, released a survey based on the public's trust and perceptions in the water sector. The survey results suggest that over time, trust has fallen in water companies' abilities to perform a range of responsibilities, including ensuring good quality drinking water and providing a reliable service.¹⁰

d. *Lack of awareness about practical opportunities for public participation in water management practice*

Research on attitudes towards public participation suggests that there is a lot of appetite to participate in tackling big societal challenges, such as effective water management. However, it is a lack of awareness about these opportunities, not a lack of interest, that is a barrier to participation. The implementation of the European Flood Directive 2007/60/EC¹¹ requires the establishment of public participation mechanisms to ensure citizens' involvement in the flood management cycle. This raises challenges on how to achieve this goal and successfully translate the directive into meaningful and effective participation.¹²

⁴ <https://www.riverthame.org/water-quality-monitoring-network>

⁵ The WFD requires river water bodies to have a catchment area greater than 10 km² and lakes to have an area of > 50 ha.

⁶ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9430020/>

⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901118306361>

⁸ <https://www.hlp.city/articles/a-new-wave-in-engagement-making-a-splash-in-the-water-sector>

⁹ <https://research.ncl.ac.uk/upstream/pilotsites/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ofwat.gov.uk/publication/trust-and-perceptions-peoples-views-on-the-water-sector-full-report/>

¹¹ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/eudr/2007/60#:~:text=The%20purpose%20of%20this%20Directive,with%20floods%20in%20the%20Community>

¹² <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901114002457>

Citizen science is an approach that involves members of the public in voluntarily contributing to research, including by asking research questions, collecting and/or analysing data, and using the results. Citizen science projects can be initiated with a range of goals and outcomes in mind. For example, in the CompAir project, citizens collect air quality data across Europe using easy-to-use sensors supplied by the project.¹³ This has helped to identify hotspots of poor air quality in specific neighbourhoods leading to changes in local and regional policies.¹⁴ For water-related examples of citizen science initiatives, see below.

The unique characteristics of citizen science mean it both engages people and empowers them, augmenting traditional monitoring as people become active in their local environment. Data generated by citizen science groups have become an increasingly important source for scientists working on biodiversity and environmental pollution, and institutions or agencies pursuing the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Citizen science is growing in the area of water management, with increasing public involvement in monitoring water resources, climate variables, water quality, and in mapping and modelling exercises. Interesting ways in which citizen science has been used in water management include the following:

- **Identifying water pollution hot spots and river flow levels**

The rise in citizen science monitoring has generated opportunities to overcome many barriers and fill data gaps. Citizen science for water quality monitoring involves inexpensive and hands-on (manual) methods or visual (qualitative) observations, often accompanied by simple gauges, test kits, taking photographs using smartphones, or collecting samples that are then sent to a laboratory for detailed analysis.¹⁵ However, a framework that captures the essential elements of effective citizen science is needed to ensure both the sustainability of volunteer engagement and data quality.

The community-led continuous water quality monitoring process of the UpStream project in the UK and Taiwan,¹⁶ highlights how the use of cost-effective, open source, continuous sensors can be paired with citizen science activities involving the public to generate highly detailed data to improve water quality. The DRYvER project,¹⁷ led by the French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), developed a unique open-source smartphone app: DRYRivERS to better understand flow intermittence in rivers. By January 2023, DRYRivERS had 1,277 users who had logged more than 4,200 observations on 1,900 waterways in Europe and around the world. Users came from 19 countries, of which 41% are in Hungary, 31% are in France, 6% are in Spain and 5% are in Czechia. Data collected from the DRYRivERS app allows for real-time monitoring of rivers and supplies precious information to river managers. The Syndicat de la Rivière d'Ain Aval et ses Affluents (SR3A) is a public authority responsible for managing the river Ain catchment, in France. SR3A is using the DRYRivERS app rather than implementing water level in situ sensors. Without citizen science smartphone apps, SR3A would not have been able to closely monitor the hydrological states of the catchment, because of both time and budget restrictions.¹⁸

In another project using the DRYRivERS app, researchers modelled flow intermittency on the basis of 15,791 hydrological state observations across four catchments in four European countries (Finland, France, Hungary and Spain). Researchers wanted to assess whether complementing standard flow gauging station data with crowdsourced observations of hydrological state to calibrate a hydrological model improved the model's predictions of river flow intermittency. The study showed that crowdsourced observations improved the performance of the modelling of hydrological states of intermittent rivers and ephemeral streams, especially in catchments where hydrological stations are scarce or when field campaigns cannot be implemented.¹⁹

¹³ <https://www.wecompair.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://eurocities.eu/latest/the-power-of-citizen-science-to-tackle-the-pollution-crisis/>

¹⁵ <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/environmental-science/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2024.1371048/full>

¹⁶ <https://research.ncl.ac.uk/upstream/>

¹⁷ <https://www.dryver.eu/citizen-science/>

¹⁸ <https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/73/7/513/7223627?login=false>

¹⁹ <https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/73/7/513/7223627?login=false>

- **Co-creation of water management strategies**

The lack of public trust in effective water management has highlighted the need to be more transparent with the public, and keep individuals better informed on the actions being taken by suppliers. By providing clarity in engagement, the public can keep updated and help alleviate the chances of backlash when projects or actions take place. The continuous water quality monitoring process of the UpStream project fostered engagement with local people, raised awareness, and encouraged collaboration through co-design activities and some monitoring stewardship. Bridging the gap between data creators and data users not only makes processes more efficient but also offers an educational experience that engages citizens and other stakeholders who would normally remain excluded and helps to build trust. The Evenlode Catchment Partnership (ECP)²⁰ convenes a multi-stakeholder group to improve the river environment, deal with pollution in the river Evenlode, UK, and to co-create river management plans with local communities. Through monitoring activities, volunteers identified the locations and timings of negative impacts on water quality, including several related to water treatment plants along the river. They are now in direct dialogue with the water company, the Environment Agency and other stakeholders about developing potential mitigation actions.²¹

- **Reporting against international water monitoring standards**

Citizen science initiatives can help achieve effective stakeholder coordination and targeting of resources by enabling people to monitor the actions and follow-through of institutions, industry and government, increasing accountability and transparency of progress in relation to commitments. Digital tools are helping to shift the scale of action by supporting people to take more coordinated and effective actions. The Ghana Marine Litter project²² generated locally-produced data for monitoring marine litter in Ghana, fostering more efficient data collection through the development of a standardised monitoring protocol. The data collection approach was developed in collaboration with staff from the National Statistics Office, helping to ensure that it could be used for official monitoring as part of Ghana's reporting on SDG targets.

- **Local stewardship, cleanup and oversight of water bodies**

The Marzenego River MICS project²³ in Italy used co-design workshops to build a common understanding of the problems related to the river and wetlands, and to identify priorities for citizen monitoring. "River contracts" - official contracts where citizens volunteer for water monitoring/stewardship - were key enablers for the success of the project. The project went to great lengths to ensure that participants were involved in multiple stages of the project, being offered different levels of involvement depending on their individual interests and availability. The Ghana Marine Litter project also contributed towards group level impacts such as increased community resilience and reduced local littering through beach cleanups.²⁴ The project Hello Environment Agency²⁵ has helped to enhance flood risk communication and community engagement across numerous locations in the UK. The platform provides real-time updates on flood defences and improvements, while also collecting valuable community feedback. By offering educational resources on flood risks, the digital assistant is helping residents and visitors stay informed and prepared, ultimately supporting the resilience and sustainability of the coastal area.

THE BENEFITS OF CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR INSTITUTIONS AND FOR PARTICIPANTS

The potential benefits of citizen science for institutions and individuals are manifold.

For institutions:

- Citizen science can provide improved data resolution for water monitoring, including the integration of traditional and non-traditional data sources, which can enhance hydrological modelling .

²⁰ <https://www.wildoxfordshire.org.uk/evenlode/evenlode-catchment-partnership>

²¹ https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10195394/2/Skarlatidou_1-s2.0-S1462901124001886-main.pdf

²² <https://www.undp.org/acceleratorlabs/untapped/case-studies/ghana-marine-litter-project>

²³ <https://about.mics.tools/project/case-studies/marzenego-river>

²⁴ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41893-022-00980-y>

²⁵ <https://www.hlp.city/case-studies/flood-resiliency-and-awareness>

- Citizen science can play a key role in helping to fill key data gaps by mobilising citizens to generate real-time localised data from water bodies that aren't covered within River Basin Districts, by tapping into community observations to ground-truth findings from surveys and other data.
- Citizen science can assist with cost-effective environmental monitoring and engagement and improved time efficiency in monitoring tasks. Using digital tools can also help increase reach while reducing operational costs.
- Co-creating monitoring plans, and tailoring citizen science initiatives to address the priorities of a wide range of end users, can help to better understand public demands. It can also help to mitigate negative public attitudes and restore public trust in institutions, contributing to better and more sustainable long-term solutions to water management.

For individuals:

- Citizen science activities can provide opportunities for participation in water quality monitoring, can foster collaboration, and can integrate local knowledge about water bodies, leading to enhanced community resilience.
- Whilst engagement and participation levels may be different across projects, citizen science can facilitate connections between the public and experts on local water management issues, and empower people to more effectively take action in their immediate surroundings.
- Citizen science initiatives can increase knowledge and understanding of water science. They can also increase understanding of the complexities of water management issues, raising awareness of things citizens can do, individually and collectively, to tackle complex water quality and, for example, flood risk issues, together.
- By soliciting contributions from a diverse range of people, citizen science can help to uncover a wider range of insights for more informed decision making, and to help build collective understanding of effective water management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Mainstreaming citizen science and citizen-led data can shift stakeholders at all levels towards more effective water management and environmental policies.²⁶

Recommendations for local authorities and municipalities:

- Promote opportunities to contribute to water management through media and advertising campaigns. Focus messaging on local and community benefits to drive participation. Collaborate with national level water sector actors to coordinate efforts.
- Enhance the capacity of local governments (both in terms of staff and resources) to combine citizen-generated data and other non-traditional data sources with official datasets for environmental monitoring.
- Collaborate and share learning so that local authorities and municipalities wishing to incorporate citizen science into their water monitoring and management practices, can receive data from citizen science projects run by third parties, and to run their own citizen science initiatives.

Recommendations for national level water sector actors and agencies:

- Nominate a focal point within institutions and agencies to map the opportunities for citizen science to contribute to water management by identifying gaps in national monitoring and implementation capacity.
- Focal points can liaise directly with citizen science initiatives and community organisations, highlighting existing data gaps and opportunities to influence decisions. This will help maximise the impact of these initiatives and to support the building of public trust in institutions responsible for water management.
- Plan the resources needed for implementation. These include the scientific design of citizen science initiatives, strategies to promote engagement and collaboration with volunteers, and the overall framework that allows national authorities and citizen scientists to share data and work together.

Recommendation for the European Commission's Directorate General for the Environment:

- Future funding mechanisms should foster institutional partnerships with municipalities, agencies and citizen science initiatives. These can help to enhance matchmaking between stakeholders, and to ensure that citizen science initiatives are specifically designed to meet the (data) needs of the partner organisations.

²⁶ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_18

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